

How to re-run Pakistan BASE scenarios

This research modelled three BASE scenarios using OSeMOSYS to identify the technologies to support energy security during renewable energy transition in Pakistan. These scenarios include: Least Cost (LC), Fossil Fuel Future (FF), Net Zero CO₂ emissions by 2050 (NZ).

To effectively run the platform, Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) provides free starter data kits which can be further updated, adapted and applied by policy-makers, consultants and academics among others. For the purpose of this study, a starter data kit for Pakistan was developed following the methodology outlined in Cannone *et al.* (2022). All data was retrieved from open-sources and inserted into the data collection and manipulation tool (DaCoMaTool), an excel workbook designed to facilitate the creation of such kit. Access to data is often a barrier for energy modelling in developing countries such as Pakistan, therefore, this study used assumptions when needed.

Least Cost (LC)

The *Least Cost (LC)* scenario assumes there will be no new policies interventions in the energy sector and models the most cost-effective way to meet demand and can't therefore be considered as a BAU scenario. Its utility proves efficient when comparing results with other scenarios modelled under specific policies and targets. Four constraints were applied and maintained in the *FF* and *NZ* scenarios for consistency. Reduced timeslices (from 96 to 8) have been applied to increase the speed of model operation and to reflect the level of energy data granularity available for Pakistan. Also, technologies and commodities required to meet transport demand have been removed as including these produced results with a much higher fossil fuel capacity to fulfil a higher power demand than is possible in Pakistan. The technology that represents transmission imports in the power sector (PWRTRNIMP) has also been removed to investigate how Pakistan will meet electricity demand domestically. In addition, the biomass power plant (PWRBIO001) technology was constrained to 1.4% of 2030 electricity demand based on IRENA's 2018 analysis to reduce its domination of Pakistan's electricity generation.

Least Cost (LC) Scenario Model Parameter Changes

- Discount Rate turned from 0.05 to 0.1
- Reduced Timeslices from 96 to 8
 - ▶ Yearsplit value changed to 0.125 (1/8)
 - ▶ Change all power plant Capacity Factors from 96 to 8
 - ▶ Change Specified Demand Profile for RESELC, COMELC and INDELC from 96 to 8
- Turn off transport
 - ▶ Accumulated Annual Demand change to 0 for TRAMCY, TRACAR, TRABUS
 - ▶ Capacity to Activity Unit (time independent variable) to 0 for DEMTRAIEVC, DEMTRAMCYELC, DEMTRACARELC, DEMTRAMCYGSL, DEMTRACARGSL, DEMTRABUSGSL, BSTOPCAR, BSTOPBUS
- Turn off PWRTRNIMP
 - ▶ Total Technology Annual Upper and Lower Limits to 0 for PWRTRNIMP
- PWRBIO constrained to 1.4% of 2035's energy demand (to avoid domination)
 - ▶ Total Technology Annual Activity Lower and Upper Limits changed to values in Appendix 1.1

Fossil Future (FF)

The *Fossil Future (FF)* scenario was based on the *LC* scenario with all new capital investment into renewable energy technologies throughout the entire modelling period constrained to zero. In other words, the model is constrained to only invest in fossil fuel technologies.

Fossil Future (FF) Scenario Model Parameter Changes
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Total Annual Max Capacity Investment constrained to 0 between 2015 and 2070 for: Wind, Solar PV, CSP, Hydropower (Large, Medium, Small).

Net Zero by 2050 (NZ)

Historical CO₂ emissions between 2015 and 2019 are used to calculate the average percentage increase of emissions, then extrapolated to peak in 2030 before reaching a linear decrease to 0 by 2050. Based on this, the *Net Zero by 2050 (NZ)* scenario constrains the maximum capacity investment for primary fossil fuel and biomass production technologies, as well as nuclear. Activity of renewable technology is then projected to meet demand.

Net Zero by 2050 (NZ) Scenario Model Parameter Changes
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Constrain Total Annual Maximum Capacity Investment<ul style="list-style-type: none">▶ For nuclear constrain to 99999 from 2015 to 2020 (PWRNUC)▶ Constrain primary fossil fuel and biomass production technologies (IMPBIO; IMPHFO; IMPLFO; MINBIO; MINCOA; IMPCOA; IMPNGS; MINNGS; MINOIL; IMPOIL)

Data sources

The data used in this paper can be found in CCG's Starter Data Kit, generated by Nájera-Aguirre (2023). Data source references can be found in the annexes of "*Input Data & Assumptions for Pakistan*" file on Zenodo.

References

Cannone *et al.* (2022a) Selected 'Starter kit' energy system modelling data for selected countries in Africa, East Asia, and South America (#CCG, 2021). Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352340922002323>

Nájera-Aguirre, A. (2023). Input Data & Assumptions for Pakistan. Zenodo Repository. [Online]